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Open Science Guidebook: Open Access Publishing

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Open science has revolutionized the field of scholarly publishing and open access (OA) publishing in its various forms has been in development already for a long time. Open access publishing is a model for scholarly communication that makes research information available to readers at no cost, as opposed to the traditional subscription model in which readers have access to scholarly information by paying a subscription.

1. WHAT

Open access publishing makes all types of scholarly literature accessible free of charge and often carries less restrictive copyright and licensing barriers than traditionally published works, for both the users and the authors. Instead of financing their operations by collecting subscription fees, open access journals generally generate income from fees charged to the authors, also known as article processing charges (APCs). Hence, the costs of editing the journal are passed on from readers, or in practice from academic libraries that subscribe to scholarly literature, to authors. It is good to keep in mind, however, that most open-access journals are financing their operation in some other way than by APCs. Usually, the journals are published and funded by scientific associations, universities and higher education institutions or other academic organizations.

Over the years, complementary but parallel forms to OA have been advocated. Some research funders give recommendations and restrictions related to them in their funding terms. Also, several countries have separate national recommendations and research organizations may also have their own policy guidelines in relation to different forms of OA publishing. Currently researchers can choose from the following forms of OA publishing:

- **Green OA** publishing refers to the self-archiving of published or prepublication works for free public use. Authors provide access to preprints or post prints (with publisher's permission) in an institutional or disciplinary archive.
- **Gold OA** publishing refers to works published in an open access journal and accessed via the journal's or publisher's website. APCs are paid by the author.
- **Hybrid OA** offers authors the option of making their articles open access, for a fee. Journals that offer hybrid OA are still fundamentally subscription journals with an open access option for individual articles. They are not true open access journals.
- **Diamond OA** publishing describes journals that are completely free to publish and to read. The costs of maintaining and publishing the journal are usually borne by the organization that sponsors the journal. Diamond OA status has no impact on the journal's peer review process. By making articles completely free both to publish and to read, Diamond OA best approaches the goals of democratizing and widely distributing academic scholarship.

The self-archiving of research publications is one cost free option that achieves openness, and most publishers allow the self-archiving of the accepted version of a manuscript. However, when an article is self-archived in the publication archive, many publishers want to place an embargo on it even if the self-archived version is the final draft of the final peer-reviewed manuscript. These embargoes vary usually from 6 to 36 months. Some publishers do not use embargoes at all. In such a case, the article can be self-archived immediately after publication.

Although OA publishing has generally been seen as beneficial, the development of OA publishing has increased the number of harmful, questionable and even fraudulent publishers on the market. These publishers are only in it for collecting large author fees and usually their peer review process does not fulfil the generally accepted requirements. These kinds of publishers are often called predatory publishers.

2. WHY

The reasons for OA publishing are diverse. One of the most important advantages of open access is that it increases the visibility of academic research results. OA publishing also improves efficiency and efficacy of research and facilitates collaboration, interdisciplinary conversation and research-based innovations. Accordingly, OA publishing allows the professional, practitioner and business communities, and the interested public, to benefit from research. The wider the audience that can access and build upon the latest research, the more likely research benefits the whole society.

From a researcher's perspective, the greatest benefit of OA publishing is that it enables rapid and wide dissemination of research results. By publishing in open access, researchers can make their research results freely accessible immediately in principle and thus receive feedback from academic community more quickly. Furthermore, research results presented in OA publications may become more efficiently actualized in the form of policies, treatments, funding allocations, and decisions than results published behind paywalls. Wide availability also means more readers, more potential collaborators and more citations.

3. HOW

For those who are interested in open access (OA) publishing, it would be useful to note the following points:

- Open access publishing covers all types of peer-reviewed publications, both journal articles and books (monographs).
- Be aware of your funder's requirements related to open access. Many funders require immediate open access and use of open licenses.
- A digital object identifier (DOI) is a unique text character sequence that is used to identify digital objects, such as journal articles. Make sure that you receive a DOI also for your preprint.
- Place your works under an open content licence, such as a Creative Commons licence, if you publish them in Open Access to make them widely reusable.
- Through a range of tools and practical recourses you may identify trusted journals and publishers. There are various databases available to assist in choosing a reliable publication channel, e.g., Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB), Web of Science and Scopus.
- Use open institutional or discipline-specific archives/repositories for self-archiving and use social media and social networks for researchers to disseminate the links to your research work in open archives.

RESOURCES AND FURTHER READING

- An open access initiative by major research funders, Plan S website: <https://www.coalition-s.org/why-plan-s/>
- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) website: <https://doaj.org/>
- Sherpa Romeo (database of publishers' and journals' OA policies): <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/>
- Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) website: <https://www.doabooks.org/>
- Directory of Open Access Scholarly Resources (ROAD) website: <https://www.issn.org/services/online-services/road-the-directory-of-open-access-scholarly-resources/>
- Think. Check. Submit. website: <https://thinkchecksubmit.org/>
- Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA) website: <https://oaspa.org/principles-of-transparency-and-best-practice-in-scholarly-publishing/>
- Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) website: <https://publicationethics.org>
- Creative Commons website: <https://creativecommons.org/choose/>
- Greussing et al. (2020) Drivers and Obstacles of Open Access Publishing. A Qualitative Investigation of Individual and Institutional Factors. *Frontiers in Communication*, vol. 5, pp. 1-13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2020.587465>

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